

The Role of IoT in Hydroponic Plant Disease Detection: A Survey of Recent Advances

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Abstract— Hydroponic agriculture offers a sustainable and efficient method for food production, but faces challenges related to disease management. Early detection of plant diseases is crucial for mitigating losses and ensuring optimal yield. The Internet of Things (IoT) presents a powerful tool for monitoring and managing hydroponic systems, enabling real-time data collection and analysis for disease detection. This literature survey aims to provide a comprehensive overview of current research in the field of hydroponic plant disease detection using IoT. The review examines various approaches, including sensor networks, image processing, machine learning (ML), and deep learning (DL) techniques. We analyze the strengths and limitations of existing studies, highlighting key challenges such as sensor selection, data integration, and model accuracy. Furthermore, we explore emerging trends and identify promising future directions for research in this field, including the development of robust disease diagnosis systems, integration with precision agriculture practices, and advancements in artificial intelligence for disease prediction and control. This review serves as a valuable resource for researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders involved in developing innovative and effective IoT-based solutions for disease management in hydroponic systems.

Keywords— Plant disease detection, crop health, hydroponics, IoT, Machine Learning, Image Processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydroponic farming, an innovative method of growing plants without soil, has gained significant traction due to its efficiency in resource use and potential for high yield. However, like traditional agriculture, hydroponic systems are susceptible to plant diseases, which can severely impact productivity and crop quality. Early and accurate detection of these diseases is crucial for maintaining the health and efficiency of hydroponic systems. The integration of IoT technologies presents a promising solution for this challenge, offering real-time monitoring and automated diagnostics.

IoT-based disease detection systems employ a network of sensors and devices to continuously monitor environmental parameters and plant health indicators. These systems leverage advanced technologies such as machine learning, artificial intelligence, and data analytics to identify disease symptoms and predict outbreaks. The application of IoT in hydroponics not only enhances disease management but also optimizes overall crop management practices by providing actionable insights and automated responses.

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive literature survey on the current state of research in the field of hydroponic plant disease detection using IoT technologies. By analyzing and synthesizing recent studies, this survey will highlight key methodologies, technological advancements, and the practical implications of IoT-based solutions. Additionally, it will identify existing gaps in the literature and suggest future research directions to further enhance the efficacy of IoT in hydroponic disease management. This literature survey serves as a valuable resource for researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders involved in developing innovative and effective IoT-based solutions for plant disease management in hydroponic systems.

II. REVIEW SELECTION METHODOLOGY

This study aims to comprehensively explore recent advancements in IoT technology for automating plant disease detection. Through careful examination and analysis of published literature in the field, it serves as a valuable resource for understanding IoT basics in smart agriculture, aiding future research endeavors. A systematic review of existing literature was conducted, using keywords like "Disease Detection," "Plant Health," "Precision Agriculture," "IoT in Hydroponics," "Automated Crop Health," and "Automated Nutrient Control" in scholarly databases. A total of 24 papers were identified initially, with subsequent selection based on relevance to technology and automation types. Following a two-step shortlisting process, 16 papers were included in this study.

III.LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, a comparative examination is conducted on 16 IoT-based automated plant disease detection systems in smart farming settings, as sourced from existing research (see Table 1). These systems are assessed across four key criteria:

- (i) The research study's objective
- (ii) The proposed solution for achieving this objective
- (iii) The methodology employed for system implementation
- (iv) The outcomes obtained following implementation.

TABLE I
LITERATURE REVIEW OF STUDIES ON PLANT DISEASE DETECTION USING IoT

Study	Objective	Proposed Solution	Methodology	Result
[4]	To develop a plant leaf disease detection system using a combination of IoT, DL and ML algorithms to achieve higher accuracy in early disease detection.	IoT: Sensors collect real-time environmental and plant data. ML (Random Forest): Predicts disease likelihood based on sensor data and past records. DL (CNN - VGG16): Analyzes plant images to classify diseases.	Data Collection: From Sensors ML Model Training: Forest model is trained on a Kaggle dataset of plant diseases. DL Model Training: A pre-trained VGG16 CNN model to classify plant disease images.	The ML model achieves an accuracy of 95.99% in predicting disease based on sensor data. The DL model achieves an accuracy of 99.2% in classifying plant disease from images.
[7]	Proposes an IoT-enabled plant disease prediction system using an improved quantum whale optimization algorithm and a deep recurrent neural network (DRDNN) to classify tomato diseases.	A system that uses an optimized DNN model and an IoT network to detect and classify plant diseases. The DNN model is trained on a publicly available dataset, and its hyperparameters are optimized using the IQWO-PCA technique.	Data Acquisition: IoT sensors. DNN Optimization using IQWO-PCA to enhance its performance. Dimensionality Reduction: PCA is employed to reduce the dimensionality of the data and improve the model's efficiency.	The proposed model performs better than traditional ML methods and DNN models with four layers. The system achieved high accuracy and low error rates when tested against various datasets.
[9]	Propose a method for automatically detecting and classifying plant diseases using a combination of machine learning and image processing techniques.	An IoT-based system combines image processing, ML, and environmental sensing to detect plant diseases. Images of leaves are analyzed for visual signs using an SVM classifier. Sensor data on temperature, humidity, and soil moisture helps predict disease outbreaks.	This system detects and predicts plant diseases using image analysis and environmental data. After collecting and preprocessing leaf images, key features are extracted and used to train an SVM classifier for disease identification. This information is then combined with sensor data to predict potential outbreaks.	The proposed system can accurately classify plant diseases and predict disease outbreaks with high accuracy rates in detecting diseases at an early stage.
[14]	To develop a smart hydroponic system that uses image recognition and ML algorithms to predict optimal nutrient delivery and detect plant diseases.	A smart hydroponic system that utilizes sensors, actuators, and ML algorithms to optimize plant growth, predict optimal nutrition delivery and detect plant diseases.	A system predicts plant nutrient levels and diseases using sensor data, images, and ML. Data is collected from sensors and cameras, preprocessed, and image features are extracted using VGG19. A Random Forest model, trained on the combined data, is then evaluated for performance.	The system achieved high accuracy in both nutrient prediction and disease detection. It outperforms previous methods in terms of accuracy and scope of application. The system is scalable, cost-effective, and energy-efficient.
[3]	To design and evaluate an image processing-based software solution for automatic detection and classification of plant leaf diseases.	The paper proposes a smart hydroponic system that uses a combination of: Image processing to detect diseases, Sensors to monitor environmental conditions and ML to analyze the data and	This system uses sensors, cameras, and machine learning to monitor plant health, predict nutrient deficiencies, and detect diseases. Data is collected, preprocessed, and image features are extracted. A trained Random	This system demonstrates superior accuracy in both nutrient prediction and disease detection compared to existing methods. Its scalability, cost-effectiveness, and energy

		predict nutrient needs and identify diseases.	Forest model predicts nutrient levels and identifies diseases.	efficiency make it a practical solution.
[13]	To develop an IoT-based system using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) for automated plant disease detection to increase efficiency and reduce labor needs.	This paper introduces a Raspberry Pi-based system for real-time plant disease detection in smart hydroponics. A deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) analyzes images from the Pi camera module to identify diseases.	The system utilizes a DCNN model trained on a dataset of 54,309 instances, encompassing 38 different classes of plant diseases affecting various crops. The model is trained using the backpropagation algorithm and evaluated using metrics like accuracy and ROC AUC.	The proposed model boasts 98% accuracy and an 88% ROC AUC score. Its successful deployment on a Raspberry Pi demonstrates its efficiency with low latency and power consumption.
[12]	To explores the use of deep learning for plant disease detection in smart hydroponic systems to enhance efficiency, reduce manpower, and improve crop yield.	This IoT platform uses sensors to monitor environmental factors impacting plant growth. Data is sent to the cloud for analysis and to inform irrigation management. Additionally, a trained CNN model uses plant images to predict diseases, allowing for early detection and intervention.	This IoT system uses sensors and a Bolt Wi-Fi module to collect and transmit environmental data to the Bolt Cloud for visualization and analysis, enabling plant monitoring. A ResNet-based model, trained on the Mohanty dataset, analyzes user-submitted leaf images to predict plant diseases, aided by techniques like one-cycle learning rate and gradient clipping for improved accuracy.	IoT System: The system successfully monitors light intensity and soil moisture levels, providing valuable data for informed irrigation practices. Plant Disease Prediction System: The CNN model achieved 99.35% accuracy on the test dataset, demonstrating its effectiveness in identifying various plant diseases.
[1]	Develop an IoT-based smart hydroponic system that uses image processing and ML algorithms to monitor plant health and optimize growing conditions.	The authors propose a DL based plant disease detection system that leverages CNNs for image classification. The system captures images of plant leaves and processes them through the trained CNN model, returning real-time disease identification and health status of the plant.	The system utilizes a CNN model trained on a large dataset of plant images with various disease classes. The authors discuss the layers of CNNs, including convolution, rectified linear unit, pooling, and fully connected layers, and highlight the role of optimization algorithms like gradient descent for model training.	The paper focuses on the technical aspects of deep learning and its application in plant disease detection. It doesn't present specific findings related to model accuracy or performance metrics, but emphasizes the potential of CNNs for this task.
[11]	Proposes an IoT and ML model to predict the probability of blister blight disease attacks on tea plants based on directly sensed crop field environmental conditions.	An IoT-based system that integrates sensors, cameras, and a cloud platform to monitor and control the hydroponic environment and Image processing algorithms analyze plant images to detect signs of stress or disease, providing real-time feedback on plant health.	This system uses a CNN model, trained on a vast plant disease image dataset, to enable disease detection. It leverages a microcontroller, sensors, and cameras to monitor environmental factors and capture plant images. Images are analyzed for features like leaf color and texture to assess plant health. The system relies on cloud infrastructure for data storage and analysis.	The system is able to accurately monitor environmental parameters and adjust hydroponic conditions accordingly. The image processing algorithms effectively detect plant health issues and provide real-time feedback.
[15]	Develop a Smart Agriculture System using IoT and ML to monitor agricultural land, detect plant diseases, and provide real-time alerts to farmers.	This solution combines an IoT network for environmental monitoring with a machine learning model to predict disease in crops. The network collects data on temperature, humidity, and rainfall, which is then analyzed by the model to identify correlations with the likelihood of blister blight outbreaks.	An IoT hardware prototype is developed to collect environmental data from the tea plantation. The collected data is analyzed to understand the correlation between environmental factors and disease intensity. An MLR model is implemented to predict the probability of a disease attack based on environmental conditions.	The model demonstrates high prediction accuracy, reaching up to 91% in 2019. The model's accuracy improves over time due to continuous feedback and retraining with new data.

[8]	Proposes an IoT-based system to help farmers identify plant diseases and provide solutions for them, aiming to increase farming efficiency and productivity.	The system utilizes a smartphone camera to capture images of diseased plant leaves. These images undergo color space conversion, segmentation with k-means clustering, feature extraction using Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrices, and classification.	Hardware: NodeMCU (ESP8266) with soil sensors. Software: Android app for live monitoring. Data: Sent to ThingSpeak. Disease Detection: VGG16 classifies tomato plants.	The paper provides a general overview of the process but does not present any specific results from the implementation of the proposed system.
[5]	Propose an IoT-based system for plant disease detection using temperature, humidity, and color sensors to monitor plant health and alert farmers.	Create an IoT system with temperature, humidity, and color sensors for plant leaf health monitoring. Transmit sensor data to a cloud platform to compare with healthy and diseased plant traits. Alert farmers of potential diseases via data analysis alerts.	The system employs DHT11 sensors for temperature and humidity and TCS3200 color sensors. Arduino UNO processes data, transmitting it to ThingSpeak. The platform compares data against a dataset to identify potential diseases.	The proposed system effectively detects diseased leaves through temperature, humidity, and color deviations from healthy leaf data, ensuring reliable and efficient early disease detection.
[10]	Develop an Internet of Things Assisted Plant Disease Detection and Crop Management System using Deep Learning for Sustainable Agriculture	An IoT system using deep learning for plant disease detection and crop management is proposed. Use sensors for real-time data collection on environmental parameters and plant health. Analyze data with deep learning to detect early disease signs. Provide farmers with timely insights for proactive interventions and optimal crop management.	The APDDCM-SHODL system includes: Preprocessing: Vector Median Filter (VMF) for image enhancement. Feature extraction: DenseNet201 model for relevant feature extraction. Hyperparameter tuning: Spotted Hyena Optimizer (SHO) for DenseNet201 optimization. Classification: Recurrent Spiking Neural Network (RSNN) for disease classification.	The APDDCM-SHODL system achieved high accuracy in detecting various plant diseases, surpassing other existing techniques. The system demonstrates improved performance in terms of accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score.
[2]	To develop a smart agriculture system for plant disease detection and irrigation management using machine learning, computer vision, and IoT technologies.	The system provides real-time, automated plant disease detection and irrigation control. It uses ResNet-50 for disease classification, IoT sensors for environmental monitoring, and a mobile app for remote monitoring and control.	Data Collection: Images are taken from the PlantVillage dataset and field observations and preprocessed and augmented using TensorFlow. Then, Features are extracted with a ResNet-50 model that classifies images into 17 disease and healthy categories. Disease Diagnosis: Decision algorithms diagnose diseases and give recommendations.	The system achieved 97.25% accuracy for potato, 90.20% for rice, and 94.55% for tomato disease classification. Integrating Raspberry Pi, NodeMCU, sensors, and a motor pump enabled effective irrigation control. The mobile app offers a user-friendly interface for monitoring and diagnosis.
[6]	Proposes an Arduino UNO-based robot equipped with an ESP32 CAM for real-time crop monitoring and disease detection using color analysis through image processing.	The proposed system offers an automated and intelligent approach to crop monitoring and disease detection. It leverages IoT technology, including sensors, actuators, and cameras, to collect real-time data and analyze it for disease identification.	Hardware: Arduino UNO, ESP32 CAM, sensors, motor driver, Bluetooth module, battery. Software: Proteus, Arduino IDE, Visual Studio Code, OpenCV. Data Collection: ESP32 CAM captures real-time crop images. Analysis: OpenCV detects and quantifies diseases. Alerts: System notifies when disease threshold is exceeded.	The system detected color changes in mangoes, bananas, tomatoes, guava, and apples, indicating disease presence. It localized diseased areas accurately and estimated disease severity. Real-time analysis and warning alerts are provided.

IV. RESEARCH GAPS

While IoT holds immense potential for revolutionizing hydroponic disease management, several research gaps hinder its widespread adoption. Addressing these research gaps is crucial for realizing the full potential of IoT in improving hydroponic plant health and productivity. To fully leverage the benefits of IoT for disease management in hydroponics, researchers must focus on overcoming the following critical research challenges (Figure 1):

Fig. 1 Research Gaps identified in the Literature Survey

Limited Data and Datasets: Most research relies on limited datasets, especially for specific hydroponic plant diseases. This makes it difficult to train robust machine learning models.

Variety of Hydroponic Environments: Datasets often lack data from different hydroponic systems, nutrient solutions, and growing conditions. This can lead to poor model generalization.

Optimal Sensor Selection: There's a need for more research on identifying the most relevant sensors for detecting specific hydroponic diseases. Different diseases may require different sensor combinations.

Data Fusion and Correlation: Integrating data from various sensors (temperature, humidity, pH, nutrient levels) with image data remains challenging. Algorithms need to be developed to effectively fuse and interpret this multi-modal data.

Sensor Calibration and Drift: Hydroponic systems can experience sensor drift over time, impacting accuracy. Robust calibration and drift correction methods need further exploration.

Specific Disease Recognition: Current systems often struggle to differentiate between various hydroponic diseases. More research is needed to develop models that can accurately identify specific diseases with high precision.

Early Stage Detection: Early detection is crucial in hydroponics. Developing models that can detect diseases at their earliest stages, before significant damage occurs, is a significant research challenge.

Environmental Variability: Hydroponic systems are sensitive to environmental changes. Research needs to address the robustness of disease detection models in various growing conditions and fluctuations.

Real-world Deployment: Bridging the gap between lab-based testing and real-world deployment is vital. Cost-effective and user-friendly solutions for hydroponic farms are needed.

Automated Interventions: Connecting disease detection with automated interventions, such as targeted nutrient adjustments or pest control measures, can significantly enhance hydroponic farm efficiency.

Closed-loop Optimization: Integrating disease detection with other smart farming technologies (like precision irrigation, lighting control) can create a closed-loop system for optimizing plant health and productivity.

Data Privacy and Security: IoT systems in hydroponics collect sensitive data. Research on data privacy and security protocols is essential for protecting information and ensuring ethical data practices.

Affordable Solutions: Cost-effective IoT solutions are essential for making these technologies accessible to smaller-scale hydroponic growers.

Scalability and Sustainability: Research on scaling these systems for larger hydroponic operations and ensuring their long-term sustainability is crucial.

Addressing these gaps is crucial for unlocking the full potential of IoT in optimizing hydroponic plant health and productivity.

V. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of IoT-based automated disease detection in hydroponics is expansive, encompassing advancements in technology, integration with other agricultural practices, and improving user accessibility and system robustness. Key areas of focus include:

Fig. 2 Future Scope of Plant Disease Detection using IoT

Expansion to Various Plant Species and Diseases:

Systems should be developed to identify a broader range of plant species and diseases, making them applicable to diverse agricultural contexts. This requires building extensive datasets and training models to recognize multiple crops and pathogens.

Enhanced Sensor Integration and Data Collection:

Incorporating sophisticated sensors to monitor additional parameters such as light intensity, pH levels, and pest presence can improve the comprehensiveness and accuracy of disease detection. More robust and reliable sensors are needed for long-term data collection in diverse hydroponic environments.

Advanced Machine Learning and Image Processing:

The development of more accurate and robust machine learning algorithms, including deep learning models, will enhance disease prediction and classification. Advanced image processing techniques should be explored to improve the identification and classification of diseases.

Real-World Implementation and Testing:

Testing these systems in real agricultural settings will help evaluate their performance under different growing conditions and with various plant species. This real-world validation is crucial for refining the systems and ensuring their practical utility.

Automation and Proactive Management:

Integration with robotics and automation can facilitate tasks such as irrigation, fertilization, and pesticide application based on real-time disease predictions. Automated intervention strategies can be developed to adjust environmental conditions and apply treatments proactively.

Cloud-Based Processing and Data Analysis:

Utilizing cloud-based storage and processing allows for real-time data analysis and model optimization. This enables continuous improvement of disease detection algorithms and supports the development of more accurate predictive models.

Blockchain for Data Security and Transparency:

Integrating blockchain technology can ensure secure and transparent data tracking, enhancing the trustworthiness of the system. This is particularly important for traceability and maintaining the integrity of the collected data.

User-Friendly Interfaces and Mobile Applications:

Developing intuitive interfaces and mobile applications will make these systems more accessible to farmers. These tools can provide real-time data analysis, disease prediction, and actionable insights, facilitating easy interpretation and decision-making.

Integration with Other Agricultural Technologies:

Combining IoT-based systems with other smart agriculture technologies, such as precision irrigation and environmental control systems, can optimize resource utilization and improve crop yield. This holistic approach to smart farming can lead to more efficient and sustainable agricultural practices.

Environmental and External Data Incorporation:

Including environmental data such as weather conditions can enhance the predictive accuracy of these systems. This broader data integration provides a more comprehensive understanding of plant health and potential disease risks.

Continuous Research and Development:

Ongoing research to develop more advanced and robust algorithms, as well as to explore the use of hybrid technologies, is essential. This includes enhancing the system's capability to detect disease severity and recommending specific treatments.

By addressing these future research directions, IoT-based automated disease detection systems in hydroponics can become more effective, reliable, and widely applicable, contributing significantly to the advancement of smart agriculture.

VI. CONCLUSION

This extensive survey has revealed the undeniable potential of IoT technology in revolutionizing hydroponic plant disease detection. Researchers are leveraging the power of sensor networks, image processing, machine learning, and deep learning to develop systems capable of detecting and predicting plant diseases with increasing accuracy. This progress leads to healthier, more productive hydroponic systems and ultimately, reduced losses for growers. Despite these remarkable strides, the field faces significant challenges that must be addressed to fully unlock the potential of IoT for hydroponic agriculture. Firstly, the lack of comprehensive and diverse datasets poses a significant hurdle. Research relies on limited datasets, often focusing on specific diseases and growing conditions, hindering the development of robust machine learning models capable of generalizing to various hydroponic environments.

Secondly, integrating data from diverse sensors with image data remains a challenge. Researchers need to develop sophisticated data fusion algorithms to effectively analyze and interpret multi-modal information from various sensors, such as temperature, humidity, pH, and nutrient levels. Additionally, sensor calibration and drift need further investigation to ensure long-term accuracy.

Finally, achieving truly effective disease detection requires tackling the specific challenges of disease recognition and early detection. Current systems often struggle to differentiate between various hydroponic diseases and need improvement to accurately identify specific pathogens. Furthermore, detecting diseases at their earliest stages, before significant damage occurs, remains a significant research challenge.

To overcome these limitations, future research must focus on several key areas. Expanding the scope of disease detection to cover a wider range of plant species and diseases is crucial for practical application. Researchers should develop more sophisticated sensors and data collection methods, further enhancing the comprehensiveness and accuracy of disease detection. The development of more accurate and robust machine learning algorithms, especially deep learning models, is also essential. This will enable more precise disease classification and prediction. The ultimate success of IoT-based disease detection in hydroponics relies on real-world implementation and testing. Bridging the gap between lab-based testing and practical agricultural settings is vital. Researchers need to create cost-effective and user-friendly solutions that are easily accessible to hydroponic growers of all scales. Furthermore, integrating disease detection with other smart farming technologies, such as precision irrigation and environmental control systems, can create a closed-loop system for optimizing plant health and productivity. This holistic approach to smart farming will lead to more efficient and sustainable agricultural practices.

Ultimately, the future of hydroponic agriculture hinges on continuous research and development. By addressing these challenges and exploring new technological advancements, IoT-based automated disease detection systems can become more effective, reliable, and universally applicable, transforming hydroponic practices and contributing to a more sustainable and efficient food system.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. A. Ahmed and S. M. Reddy, "Smart Hydroponic System and Monitoring of Plant's Health through Machine Learning," *IJRASET*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 4261–4263, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.22214/ijraset.2023.54443.
- [2] S. Islam, Md. Z. Hasan, and S. A. Kabir, "Smart Agriculture System for Plant Disease Detection and Irrigation Management Using Machine Learning and IoT," in *2023 5th International Conference on Sustainable Technologies for Industry 5.0 (STI)*, Dhaka, Bangladesh: IEEE, Dec. 2023, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/STI59863.2023.10465227.
- [3] Aju Saigal, Basheru Aremu, and Arumuga Perumal, "Plants health monitoring and prediction for precision horticulture," *World J. Adv. Res. Rev.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 967–973, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.1.0078.
- [4] Y. Harshavardhan Reddy et al., "Plant Leaf Disease Detection using IoT, DL and ML," *IJARST*, pp. 368–379, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.48175/IJARST-7888.
- [5] M. A. Nawaz et al., "Plant Disease Detection using Internet of Thing (IoT)," *IJACSA*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.14569/IJACSA.2020.0110162.
- [6] S. N. Mohtasim, J. Jahan Khan, M. Mahmudul Islam, M. K. Sarker, M. R. Uddin, and M. Hasan, "IoT-based Crop Monitoring and Disease Detection," in *2023 5th International Conference on Sustainable Technologies for Industry 5.0 (STI)*, Dhaka, Bangladesh: IEEE, Dec. 2023, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/STI59863.2023.10464923.
- [7] M. Sowmiya and S. Krishnaveni, "IoT enabled prediction of agriculture's plant disease using improved quantum whale optimization DRDNN approach," *Measurement: Sensors*, vol. 27, p. 100812, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.measen.2023.100812.
- [8] W. M. Ead and M. M. Abbassy, "IoT Based on Plant Diseases Detection and Classification," in *2021 7th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems (ICACCS)*, Coimbatore, India: IEEE, Mar. 2021, pp. 2030–2033. doi: 10.1109/ICACCS51430.2021.9441954.
- [9] K. P. Kumar, B. Singh, S. D. Bonde, and S. Rout, "IoT And Machine Learning Based Effective Plant Disease Classification And Detection For Agricultural Applications," vol. 11.
- [10] E. A. Al-Shahari, G. Aldehim, M. Aljebreen, J. S. Alqurni, A. S. Salama, and S. Abdelbagi, "Internet of Things Assisted Plant Disease Detection and Crop Management using Deep Learning for Sustainable Agriculture," *IEEE Access*, pp. 1–1, 2024, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3397619.
- [11] Z. Liu, R. N. Bashir, S. Iqbal, M. M. A. Shahid, M. Tausif, and Q. Umer, "Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning Model of Plant Disease Prediction–Blister Blight for Tea Plant," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 44934–44944, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3169147.
- [12] A. Musa, M. Hassan, and M. Hamada, "Deep Learning for Plant Disease Detection for Smart- Hydroponics".
- [13] A. Musa, M. Hamada, F. M. Aliyu, and M. Hassan, "An Intelligent Plant Disease Detection System for Smart Hydroponic Using Convolutional Neural Network," in *2021 IEEE 14th International Symposium on Embedded Multicore/Many-core Systems-on-Chip (MCSoc)*, Singapore, Singapore: IEEE, Dec. 2021, pp. 345–351. doi: 10.1109/MCSoc51149.2021.00058.
- [14] G D Kirana et al., "Nutrition Prediction and Disease Detection in Hydroponics", *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, ISSN:2349-5162, Vol.10, Issue 5, page no. ppf67-f69, May-2023, Available at : <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2305512.pdf>
- [15] Arathi Nair, Gouripriya J, Merry James, Sumi Mary Shibu, Shihabudeen H, "Smart Farming and Plant Disease Detection using IoT and ML", *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY (IJERT) NCREIS – 2021 (Volume 09 – Issue 13)*,